

Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI) & AI for Chemistry: AIChemistry

Project: Exploring the semantic landscape of the physical sciences
A Joint PSDI & AIChemistry Internship 2025 Report
2nd July - 5th September 2024

Project Student: Oscar Robinson

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1 Project Details

Project Name	Exploring the semantic landscape of the physical sciences
Project Dates	2nd July - 5th September 2024

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1.3 Project Description

This project will undertake an investigation into the semantic landscape of the physical sciences, to identify what semantic web technologies exist in this field, where they are actually being used across different domains and projects, and what the outstanding issues and barriers are.

2 Lay Summary

This project aims to explore how information and data can be organised in the physical sciences using technologies called "semantic web technologies" that aim to improve and clarify the representation and communication of data. Different research areas use their own niche terminologies and methods to describe entities within their domain; this can be a barrier when trying to combine information or communicate between different domains. Semantic web technologies aim to organise this information such that computers can better understand the data and create inferences between cross-domain knowledge - termed "machine-readable data", which makes use of **ontologies**, structured representations of the niche terminologies and entities within a domain.

A key aspect of the project involved examining how different scientific domains are utilising ontologies to organise their vast data outputs. For example, some domains such as biology and chemistry have a large number of ontologies available to choose from, whereas other fields such as materials science have very few. By analysing various online ontology repositories, the project aimed to highlight these differences in *ontological availability* and suggest further hypotheses to explore for future research.

3 Introduction

In the vast research of the physical sciences, the organisation and representation of data plays a crucial role in accelerating research and creating viable databases and repositories for future projects to build upon. The physical sciences concern diverse disciplines dealing with non-living systems and materials, including physics, chemistry, and geo-studies, all of which are established in history and as-such inherit a complex web of terminologies, theories, and *niches* that present challenges for interdisciplinary work. From a holistic perspective, the diversity of the physical science domains highlight the essential need for a framework to have a systematic and reliable approach for managing and integrating the vast research outputs of these domains.

A key-step in this framework is the understanding of the *semantic landscape*; the specific vocabulary used within each of the fields, how objects and processes are defined, their attributes, and associated classes or hierarchies. A well-structured semantic landscape permits the adherence to the FAIR data principles: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability. By leveraging semantic technologies - such as **RDF (Resource Description Framework)**, **OWL (Web Ontology Language)**, and **SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language)** - hidden relationships between data, patterns, and gaps in research, can be uncovered using computational methods and intelligent querying. These methods provide context to the information being made digitally available, termed *linked data*, whereby computers can infer relationships between isolated pockets of research (rather than recognising explicit patterns) as humans can but with the extraordinarily greater volume of data available on the web.

3.1 A history of the Semantic Web

The “Semantic Web” was first conceptualised by Tim Berners-Lee in the late 1990s as an extension to the World-Wide-Web, with the aim being to move beyond the traditional web (where information was largely unstructured and designed primarily for human consumption) to a more intelligent and structured web service that could be easily processed by machines, enabling automated ways of accessing and using information across domains. [1]

Figure 1: A typical representation of the Semantic Web layered architecture, which has undergone many variations, originally conceptualised by Tim Berners-Lee. Extracted from [2].

The development of the Semantic Web has been a gradual process, with several key technologies forming the shape of the current landscape and building upon one-another, as shown in Figure 1. The three key technologies are:

- **RDF**: a standard framework for data description in Subject-Predicate-Object triples, shown in Figure 2. The concept of RDF builds upon Syllogism (Aristotle, c.350 BCE [3]) and Predicate Logic (Gottlob Frege, 1879 [4]); historic concepts that established and developed forms of reasoning where conclusions can be drawn from two premises. The establishment of the RDF description language allowed complex relationships and properties to be expressed formally and mathematically, for machine legibility.

Figure 2: An example of a Subject-Predicate-Object triple data representation. The Amplifier is the subject, for which "sampling frequency" is being attributed to via the "has property" predicate. Extracted from [5]

- **OWL**: the primary language in Semantic Web applications, it is a knowledge representation language that builds upon RDF and is used to create **ontologies** - formal representations of concepts, terminology, and relationships, within a domain. OWL allows for more expressive descriptions of the data, including customisable rules and axioms based on computational requirements. [6]
- **SPARQL**: a query language that allows data retrieval and manipulation from databases written in RDF format. [7]

This project will focus on the exploration and availability of ontologies within the physical sciences.

3.2 An aside: life's not FAIR, why does my data need to be?

The FAIR principles are a set of guidelines set out by a consortium of scientists with the objective of improving the quality and stewardship of data output from industry or research in an effort to ensure that data is organised and documented in such a way that it is easily found, accessed, and shared, by researchers and machines alike, thereby maximising the value of the data. [8]

Findable: the first principle emphasises the importance of making data easily discoverable, for example by ensuring that all data has a unique persistent identifier such as a DOI for datasets (Digital Object Identifier). Furthermore, all data should be described with rich, relevant

metadata that defines context and content to improve the ability of users and machines to recall the data via sorting/filtering techniques, or search querying.

Accessible: the second principle ensures that once data is found, it is in such a format that it can be retrieved and used easily; the data should be accessible through standardised protocols such as HTTP on file-sharing sites such as GitHub, or if privacy restrictions mean that the data is not openly accessible then the associated metadata should include instructions of how to acquire access should it be required.

Interoperable: the third principle relates most closely to the objective of semantic technologies. For data to be interoperable, it should use common formats, languages, and standards, set out in ontologies and data models to enable different datasets to be understood together. This principle is crucial for the integration and reuse of datasets from various domains, ensuring that valid research can be understood and used universally such that repeat experiments (for example) are not needed.

Reusable: the fourth and final principle ensures that data which adheres to the above principles is made available alongside clear documentation and licensing information detailing its terms of use; extending the applications of the data beyond the original research scope and allowing it to contribute to new insights and innovations in future research.

The Semantic Web relies on data being not just openly available, but organised and described in a way that allows it to be connected across different domains. By adhering to the FAIR principles, data on the semantic web is **findable** through unique identifiers and rich metadata, **accessible** via standardised protocols, **interoperable** by adhering to data management standards and vocabularies, and **reusable** through clear documentation and licensing. On a scale as ambitious as the Semantic Web set out to be, this is a monumental task, but the ability to leverage semantic technologies on a lower-level framework e.g company-wide data management using HQDM (Section 5.5) still relies on the same principles of data stewardship and quality control fundamental to FAIR to reap the potential rewards.

3.3 Success story: Semantic Technologies and Drug Discovery

As established in *A new wave of innovation in Semantic web tools for drug discovery* by Kanza et al, Semantic Web technologies have gained traction in recent years to handle the increasing amount of data associated with pharmaceutical research, from biochemical reactions to drug-disease relationships. This paper highlights a success story of the utilisation of semantic web technologies to accelerate research output in a vital domain. By following the principles of the semantic web and linked data to formalise the representation and structure of data for drug discovery, significant advances have been made in facilitating data integration, improving information access, and enabling previously undiscovered links to be identified between pharmacological agents. Another vital aspect covered in the paper is the role of Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence in leveraging the machine-readable data that underpins the semantic technologies being employed. With this data organisation, researchers are able to accelerate sections of the drug discovery pipeline using automated processes and overcome limitations of traditional drug discovery methods such as data extraction and hypothesising drug-target interactions. [9]

4 Project Scope

This internship project for PSDI consists of two broad assignments, Task 1 and Task 2:

- **Task 1:** this task is an introduction to the Semantic Web, to familiarise the reader with how ontologies are currently being used in four key areas relevant to research in the physical sciences. It also consisted of the background research and understanding laid out in Section 3. The required deliverable for this Task is a summary comparison of the various ontologies found, in particular the Research Area categorisation (Section 5.1) that will be required for Task 2.
- **Task 2:** this task focuses on the overall ontological availability within the physical sciences. Ontology Lookup Services (OLSs) from various providers will be explored and their contents categorised based on the Research Area ontology decided upon in 5.1. This will allow for rudimentary analysis of the ontologies currently available in the physical sciences, and thus how the Semantic Web is being utilised. This task will provide the process for future research, and is not conclusive in standalone form.

5 Task 1 - Ontology exploration for four key areas

Task 1 for the project was to research four foundational areas to the understanding in describing the physical sciences and find ontologies that cover each of these, set out in 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, and 5.4, overseen by Aileen Day. Factors such as hierarchy (are there sub-domains within each of the domains), how often the lists are maintained/updated, presence of unique identifiers, how extensive the lists are, and whether or not they are simple controlled-vocabularies or fully defined ontologies, were all considered in a summary comparison of the ontologies found.

5.1 Research Area - *What are the Physical Sciences?* (EuroSciVoc)

The first section of ontology research concerned seeking a categorisation for *what the physical sciences actually are*, which was key for the rest of the project to proceed. Five research classification systems were investigated; EPSRC, ERC, DRG, EuroSciVoc, and HECOS.

- **EPSRC:** The Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council Research Areas list is a non-hierarchical categorisation system used to define and structure research funding within the physical sciences and engineering. While the system does have hierarchical elements when breaking down research contributions satisfying the conditions of certain themes, the categorisation system itself is not split into hierarchies. Each item within the category has a brief definition but does not contain a unique identifier for each term, however, the terms are used as a controlled vocabulary across all EPSRC documentation.

An example from the EPSRC list:

Algebra: Algebra stems from the study of equations, their solutions and associated operations and symmetries, including group theory, representation theory and ring theory.

Available at [\[10\]](#)

The research areas list covers the whole of Engineering and the Physical Sciences and is maintained by the UKRI (United Kingdom Research and Innovation) government agency. Changes and updates occur to the list as new research areas are identified during each funding round. PSDI is an EPSRC-funded initiative, thus adhering to this vocabulary or creating a suitable mapping is important.

- **ERC:** The European Research Council uses a hierarchical categorisation system similarly to the EPSRC, for defining research areas and allocating funding. There are three research

domains identified, which further split into 27 panels (as of the 2021/22 directive) to cover all fields of science and engineering. The three research domains are Social Sciences and Humanities with 7 panels (SH1-7), Physical Sciences and Engineering with 11 panels (PE1-11), and Life Sciences with 9 panels (LS1-9).

The domain panels for the Physical Sciences and Engineering (of interest to this summary) each include a comprehensive list of subcategories to further label each sub-discipline with a unique identifier. For example PE1.1 *Logic and foundations*, which is a subdivision of PE1 *Mathematics*. The categories are reviewed similarly to the EPSRC, periodically and aligned with funding releases. The last two updates being in 2021 and 2024 (new). [11]

- **DFG:** The Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German Research Foudation) classifies research into major scientific disciplines and sub-disciplines similarly to the ERC. However, the DRG system contains distinct hierarchies and strict designations covering all of the physical sciences, for example 3.11-01 Inorganic Molecular Chemistry (under the hierarchy Molecular Chemistry (3.31) → Chemistry (31) → Natural Sciences (3)). [12]
- **EuroSciVoc:** The European Scientific Vocabulary is an extensive ontology covering over 1000 categories in 6 languages (English, French, German, Italian, Polish, and Spanish). It is a "proper" ontology, being freely downloadable in .rdf and .ttl formats ¹ and each term has a persistent URL for identification.

Concept

thermodynamics CURRENT

Version: 1.3.1
 Concept URI: <http://data.europa.eu/8mn/euroscivoc/0fce4b31-70e0-42f1-b844-5f7f0ce74914>

[Go to asset list](#)
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UF: thermodynamic model
 heating techniques
 heating technique
 thermodynamic
 thermal stresses
 thermal application

Language equivalents
 ES [termodinámica](#)
 DE [Thermodynamik](#)
 EN thermodynamics
 FR [thermodynamique](#)
 IT [termodinamica](#)
 PL [termodynamika](#)

Last modification: 24/05/2022
Valid since: 2019-12-02
Identifier: 0fce4b31-70e0-42f1-b844-5f7f0ce74914

BT | [physical sciences](#)
 1
 BT2 | [natural sciences](#)

Figure 3: EuroSciVoc example "thermodynamics", showing the language equivalents, unique identifier, date of definition, hierarchy, as well as common locations the word is found (UF).

Extracted from [13]

- **HECOS:** The Higher Education Classification of Subjects is a controlled vocabulary of 1,092 terms to categorise courses and modules at a higher education level in the UK.

¹<https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/dataset/-/resource?uri=http://publications.europa.eu/resource/dataset/euroscivoc>

The list is non-hierarchical but each term is assigned a unique subject identifier code, and adjacent subjects are related by the code assigned to them (e.g 100036 Optometry, and 100037 Orthoptics). The coverage of the vocabulary does include fields within the physical sciences, but the specificity of the vocabulary for defining higher educational courses doesn't lend the categorisation system to evaluating research areas, and a different system would be recommended. [14]

Summary of Research Area ontologies: Based on the examples studied above, EuroSciVoc presents itself as the most beneficial for categorising research areas using semantic technologies; being an already complete and established ontology, available in multiple languages, and in a freely accessible format with clear version tracking to enable consistency and traceback of new terms and categories as they are added. While PSDI is funded by the EPSRC, and collaborates with the UKRI, the categorisation systems used here are not in ontological format and updates to the vocabulary list for future versions could require a complete re-classification for any system utilising a Research Area Classification system.

To aid this, a mapping was produced from the EPSRC Research Areas to EuroSciVoc NT1 "broader" categories using a method described and justified in Section 6, seen in Figure 4.

5.2 Substance Type - *What is being studied?* (EMMO)

The second section of ontology research concerned seeking a categorisation for *what physically is being studied*. Five classification systems were explored; ChEBI, CSD, EMMO, and ChemInf.

- **ChEBI:** The Chemical Entities of Biological Interest ontology is provided by the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI), designed primarily for the life sciences but with significant applications in the physical sciences. ChEBI covers a wide range of research areas from EuroSciVoc, with a particular focus on chemistry, chemical sciences, molecular sciences, and biological sciences. The ontology is regularly updated, and each term is assigned a unique identifier. Furthermore, each term contains extensive information regarding its chemical properties, as well as known (biological) functions, e.g in metabolism. It also contains a list of synonyms for the substance in other languages (similar to EuroSciVoc) and contains reference numbers to other databases such as the CAS Registry. Furthermore, CHEBI also allows search queries to be *three-star-only* or search-all, whereby the search result can be filtered to include only the results manually annotated by the ChEBI developer team, or include public submissions too. [15]
- **CSD:** The Cambridge Structural Database is a collection of over 1,000,000 compounds that can be visualised and downloaded, provided by the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC). It contains extensive crystallographic data for both organic and metal-organic compounds, covering key research areas such as crystallography, materials science, and solid-state chemistry. The CSD is structured as a hierarchical ontology, and is regularly maintained and updated. While not strictly an ontology, the service is an invaluable repository of substance information. [16]
- **EMMO:** The Elementary Multiperspective Materials Ontology is a framework ontology that provides a formal structure for organising and integrating perspectives on various materials. It is a very deep hierarchical ontology, allowing classification of an object from fundamental physical concepts (such as thermodynamic and quantum properties) to complex structures such as materials and devices. EMMO also considers temporality in its framework (it is a 4D ontology) - expressing that objects' properties can vary with time. EMMO also includes concepts from mereotopology (the study of part-whole relations and spatial properties) and semiotics (the study of signs and symbols). This combination of defining objects from their foundations upwards lends EMMO to be a very broad

Figure 4: EPSRC Research Areas to EuroSciVoc NT1 categories mapping shown in a Sankey diagram.

ontology with many applications, but the ontology itself does not include any examples of such objects (it is a framework) thus is not ready out-of-the-box for Substance Type classification. [17]

- **ChemInf:** The Chemical Information Ontology is widely used in cheminformatics software, databases, and research, for representing chemical information. ChemInf is particularly focused on entities relating to chemical structures, such as molecular representations, but is a smaller ontology compared to that of ChEBI. ChemInf lacks breadth compared to ontologies such as EMMO and CSD thus was not investigated further.

Summary of Substance Type ontologies: The examples studied above do not define a clear "winner" for selecting a substance type ontology, likely due to the specific requirements of a categorisation system based on the perspective of each domain using it. The most broad option would be using EMMO, but requires filling in from the ground-up with objects that are known in other databases but not defined in EMMO, requiring a heavy initial investment in time.

5.3 Technique - *How are things being studied?* (ChMO)

The third section of ontology research was focused on the techniques used in the physical sciences, for example processes for extracting chemicals or processing materials. This, and Section 5.4 were not vital for the progression of the project in Task 2 and formed only brief research for future projects thus only one ontology was selected for each instead of a full comparative study.

- **ChMO:** The Chemical Methods Ontology details a wide array of methods and techniques used in analytical chemistry, chemical synthesis, and material processing. The ontology is hierarchical and contains over 3,000 individually URI labelled classes, including methods used to collect data (e.g mass spectrometry (Figure 5) and electron microscopy), separation media such as chromatography, electrophoresis, and sample ionisation, and processes for synthesis of materials such as epitaxy and continuous vapour deposition. All instruments used in these experiments can be defined per the framework set out in the ontology, resulting in a consistent vocabulary for inter-lab communication.

The screenshot shows the EMBL-EBI Ontology Lookup Service interface. At the top, there is a breadcrumb trail: 'Ontologies > CHMO > Classes > CHMO:0000228'. To the right of the breadcrumb are icons for 'Copy', a language dropdown set to 'en', and a 'JSON' icon. The main content area is titled 'spectroscopy' and includes the following information:

- URI: http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000228 (with a 'Copy' icon)
- Description: 'The study of the interaction of a sample with radiation or particles for measurement or detection.' (with an information icon)
- 'Also appears in' section with buttons for 'MSIO' and 'PRIDE'.
- 'Synonym' section with a button for 'spectrometry'.
- A search input field with the placeholder text 'Search CHMO...' and a 'Search' button.
- Filter options: Exact match, Include obsolete terms, and Include imported terms.

Figure 5: "spectroscopy" example from ChMO online search using the EMBL-EBI Ontology Lookup Service. Extracted from [18]

Furthermore, ChMO is designed to work complementary with the OBI (Ontology for Biomedical Investigations) and is in the process of being combined with ChemInf, OBI, and ChEBI, to create an overarching 'Chemical Analysis Ontology', CAO.

5.4 Property Type - *What fundamental properties do objects have?* - (OM)

The last section of ontology research regards consistency in the dimensional properties of quantities being measured, naturally this lends itself to the **Ontology of units of Measure - OM**. This hierarchical ontology models concepts and relationships foundational to scientific research, detailing units, quantities, measurements, and dimensions. This ontology is widely used in scientific research and covers a wide range of International System of Units (SI) and non-SI units to ensure consistent unit definitions across domains, which are often critical to experimental success. An example is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: "length" example from OM online search using the EMBL-EBI Ontology Lookup Service. Extracted from [19]

5.5 Another aside: the HQDM framework

The **High-Quality Data Model** framework is an approach to supporting data management in complex systems and domains by utilising semantic web technologies to facilitate data interoperability and consistency. HQDM provides a formalised way to define entities within a domain (such as people, organisations, or machines) and their relationships as a function of time, providing temporal constructs (similar to EMMO, Section 5.2) that permit modelling of how entities change properties over time. This is key for areas such as business management, infrastructure engineering, and manufacturing.

A fundamental aspect of HQDM is the use and design of high-quality ontologies for domain specific knowledge and establishing mappings between adjacent domains to facilitate effective communication and data integration in potentially disparate systems, e.g in manufacturing where procurement, finances, production, and R&D departments have to share information seamlessly. As ontologies (and the semantic web as a whole) are underpinned by formal, axiomatic mathematical logic, sophisticated logical reasoning systems can be used to check for inconsistencies between ontologies used within domains and provide inferences based on the data provided. This is vital for safety-critical operations.

To adopt the use of HQDM, a system would:

- **Utilise** pre-existing HQDM-compliant ontologies or develop new domain-specific ontologies relevant to the system purpose

- **Incorporate** temporal constructs to represent real-world system processes and their variations over time (e.g employment status for employees)
- **Integrate** the vast data sources from the system following the principles of semantic technologies to ensure data interoperability
- **Leverage** logic-reasoning tools to ensure the data-stewardship standards set by HQDM are being adhered-to, and that any information passes consistency checks based on the ontologies being employed.

6 Task 2 - Ontological availability

Task 2 forms the main bulk of work done for the project, building on the foundational understanding developed during Task 1, in particular Section 5.1. The objective of the task was to explore the availability of ontologies for Research Areas (RAs) across the physical sciences, following the flowchart in Figure 7.

6.1 Methodology

Figure 7: Task 2 Methodology Flowchart

- **Define ontology information required:** For the analysis of ontological availability, key pieces of metadata need extracting from each ontology via its respective Ontology Lookup Service (OLS) using a web scraper. This metadata includes:
 - **Ontology ID** for identification of the ontology and removal of duplicates, e.g CHEBI.
 - **Ontology Name** likewise to the Ontology ID, e.g Chemical Entities of Biological Interest.
 - **Ontology Description** to aid the classification of Research Area using the description as a prompt, e.g ”A structured classification of chemical compounds of biological relevance”.
 - **Ontology URL** to provide back-tracing of the selected ontologies and cross-reference with other OLSs.
 - **Ontology Repository** the OLS from which the ontology came from, e.g BioPortal.
 - **Assigned Category** identified any user or site-assigned categories to the ontology. For example, many BioPortal ontologies have their own categories that can aid the classification of RA.
- **Find OLS:** 11 ontology repositories were selected for analysis, shown in Figure 8. These sites act as hubs for public access of openly available ontologies across a wide range of domains.

The OntoPortal Alliance is a consortium of research infrastructure teams that use the collaboratively developed OntoPortal software and covers 7 of the 11 identified repositories, the remaining 4 are run by independent research organisations, as shown in Table 1.

Figure 8: The 11 Ontology Lookup Services identified for analysis, covering a wide range of the physical sciences.

- **Design HTML scraper:** Once each OLS was found, a HTML web-scraper was designed in Python using Selenium WebDriver. While not designed primarily for web scraping, many repository sites had unconventional HTML structures, pagination, and dynamic loading, that required a more-manual approach to automated data harvesting. The process involved analysing the website structure using inbuilt HTML viewers, and instructing the WebDriver to access the information stored under specific uniform elements across the webpage as seen in Figure 9. [31]

OLS Name	Description	Number of Ontologies (without duplicates)	Citation
AgroPortal	OntoPortal for Agronomy, Agri-food and related domains	142	[20]
BioPortal	OntoPortal for Biomedical ontologies	1,053	[21]
EarthPortal	OntoPortal for Earth Sciences and Environmental data	40	[22]
EcoPortal	OntoPortal for Ecology and related domains	27	[23]
IndustryPortal	OntoPortal for Industrial Engineering and related domains	106	[24]
MatPortal	OntoPortal for Materials Science and related domains	31	[25]
BiodivPortal	OntoPortal for Biodiversity and related domains	14	[26]
EMBL-EBI	OLS run by the European Molecular Biology Laboratory - European Bioinformatics Institute, consisting mainly of biomedical/biological ontologies	136	[27]
BioRegistry	Community curated registry containing a range of ontologies from across the physical sciences, primarily relating to the Life Sciences	1,482	[28]
TIB (NFDI)	The terminology service run by NFDI, providing a repository for ontologies from domains such as architecture, chemistry, computer science, mathematics, and physics.	155	[29]
LOV	Linked Open Vocabularies provides a repository for linked data vocabularies (ontologies) from community-driven data publishers and ontology designers from a wide range of RAs.	505	[30]

Table 1: Ontology repositories selected for investigation

```

<div class="grid-75">
  <!-- before -->
  <!-- ngIf: ontology.type == 'ontology_view' -->
  <div style="font-size: 1.2em;">
    <a href="/ontologies/MEDDRA/" class="ng-binding">
      <!-- ngIf: debug -->
      <!-- ngIf: ontology.private -->
      </a>
      <!-- ngIf: ontology.private -->
      </div>
      <!-- ngIf: ontology.submission -->
      <div ng-if="ontology.submission" class="ng-scope">
        <div style="margin-bottom: 5px;" class="ng-binding">
          <small>MEDDRA is an international medical terminology, with an emphasis on use for data entry, retrieval, analysis, and display</small>
        </div>
        <span class="ont-info ng-binding"></span>
        <!-- ngIf: facets.forecast.active.length > 1 -->
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>

```

Figure 9: A sample of the HTML code extracted from the BioPortal repository, detailing the Ontology *Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities Terminology, MedDRA*, and the description assigned to it. This information is passed into the web-scraper.

Ontology ID	Ontology Name	Ontology Description	URL	Ontology Repository	Category (misc.)
MEDDRA	Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities Terminology	MedDRA is an international medical terminology with an emphasis on use for data entry, retrieval, analysis, and display	https://bio BioPortal		Health
SNOMEDCT	SNOMED CT	SNOMED Clinical Terms	https://bio BioPortal		Health
RXNORM	RxNORM	RxNorm Vocabulary	https://bio BioPortal		Health
NDDF	National Drug Data File	National Drug Data File Plus Source Vocabulary	https://bio BioPortal		Health
RCD	Read Codes, Clinical Terms Version 3	Clinical Terms Version 3 (CTV3) (Read Codes) (Q199): National Drug Data File Plus Source Vocabulary	https://bio BioPortal		No categories available

Figure 10: The *OntologyList.xlsx* dataset, duplicate entries are discussed later in 6.2.

- **Export ontologies:** After each round of web-scraping, the Python script would export the located ontologies to a *.csv* file, which is then **merged into one dataset** called *OntologyList.xlsx* for further analysis (Figure 10).
- **Categorisation using LLM’s (GPT-4o, GEMINI, Copilot):** Once the ontology metadata is accumulated into one spreadsheet, the following instructions were given to the LLM to categorise the ontologies by Research Area. The EuroSciVoc "NT1" level categorisation system was used as shown below. This gave a sufficiently broad categorisation for all ontologies. [13]

Social Sciences

- Economics and Business
- Psychology
- Educational Sciences
- Law
- Sociology
- Social Geography
- Media and Communications
- Political Sciences
- Other Social Sciences

Humanities

- Languages and Literature
- Philosophy, Ethics, and Religion
- Arts
- History and Archaeology
- Other Humanities

Agricultural Sciences

- Agricultural Biotechnology
- Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries
- Veterinary Sciences
- Animal and Dairy Science

Other Agricultural Sciences

Medical and Health Sciences

- Health Sciences
- Medical Biotechnology
- Basic Medicine
- Clinical Medicine
- Other Medical Sciences

Natural Sciences

- Earth and Related Environmental Sciences
- Mathematics
- Biological Sciences
- Chemical Sciences
- Physical Sciences
- Computer and Information Sciences
- Other Natural Sciences

Engineering and Technology

- Chemical Engineering
- Industrial Biotechnology
- Other Engineering and Technologies
- Civil Engineering

- Electrical Engineering, Electronic Engineering, Information Engineering
- Environmental Engineering
- Nanotechnology
- Medical Engineering
- Environmental Biotechnology
- Materials Engineering
- Mechanical Engineering

Task:

- Assign each of the ontologies in the spreadsheet appropriate EuroSciVoc NT1 categories (more than one category can be assigned per ontology), based on the ontology names and descriptions using an iterative algorithm that explores related terms and synonyms.
- Use the outlier category "unassigned" for those which do not fit the current criteria; aim to minimise the number of unassigned ontologies at each iteration.

This task statement resulted in the following iterative classification algorithm from the LLM (generated in GPT-4o):

- Round 1:**
 - **Approach:** The first round applied a broad set of predefined terms associated with each EuroSciVoc NT1 category.
 - **Result:** This round classified many ontologies correctly but still left a significant number as "unassigned" due to strict matching with predefined terms.
- Round 2:**
 - **Approach:** In the second round, the classification criteria were relaxed slightly. Broader synonyms and related terms were considered, along with some contextual inference based on the ontology name and description.
 - **Result:** This round significantly reduced the number of "unassigned" categories, especially for ontologies with names that closely matched specific terms.
- Round 3:**
 - **Approach:** For any remaining unassigned entries, the classification attempted to identify more generalised terms, focusing on capturing the broader context of each ontology.
 - **Result:** Categories such as "other engineering and technologies", "agriculture, forestry, and fisheries", and "health sciences", were populated more effectively. This round helped capture ontologies that did not directly match specific terms but were clearly relevant to broader fields.
- Round 4:**
 - **Approach:** Focused on ontologies that remained unassigned after the third round, terms from associated fields or disciplines were considered, even if they were loosely connected.
 - **Result:** Further reduction in unassigned entries, particularly by classifying items into interdisciplinary or less obvious categories such as "natural sciences" and "industrial biotechnology".
- Round 5:**
 - **Approach:** In the final round, the logic incorporated more general associations across multiple disciplines to capture any ontologies that had been difficult to classify.
 - **Result:** Nearly all ontologies were assigned categories, with minimal reliance on the "unassigned" label. This round ensured that broad or interdisciplinary ontologies were given suitable classifications, even if loosely fitting multiple categories.

6.2 Results

After ontology scraping and exporting, the dataset `OntologyList.xlsx` contained 4,669 individual ontologies. There were 1,110 identified duplicates across the list which were manually removed, at each stage selecting for the ontology which had the most-rich metadata available to aid classification, this leaves a dataset of 3,693 unique ontologies in the distribution shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Distribution of ontologies by repository in the final dataset, with duplicates removed.

Due to time limitations in the project, the only LLM that was used for classification was GPT-4o. This means that the classifications made were not cross-comparable and the study would benefit from this to ensure the classification of RA is accurate and reliable. Despite this, the initial investigation still presents some interesting data. Plotting the distributions of EuroSciVoc NT1 categories assigned produces Figure 12, which highlights clearly the large number of *computer and information sciences* ontologies, especially within the BioRegistry repository, likely relating to any informatics subdomains such as cheminformatics and bioinformatics, or any data analysis within these domains. However, what is also clear is that the classification system was not foolproof; evidenced by the high number of *unassigned* category ontologies, and the large number of *arts* RA ontologies present despite no "arts" being the key topic for any of the repositories.

Figure 12: The distribution of all EuroSciVoc categories from the ontology list extracted from the 11 OLSs.

Figure 13: Distribution of specified EuroSciVoc categories of relevance to the physical sciences.

The issues identified may arise due to misclassification, but in an effort to mitigate this the classification system was asked to assign multiple RAs to each ontology where no obvious decision could be made. This may likely have resulted in several ontologies that focus on annotating diagrams for example in subdomains of Anatomy being incorrectly classified as "arts". To better select the Research Areas of interest (reflecting the physical sciences), the EuroSciVoc NT1 categories belonging to *Social Sciences*, *Humanities*, *Agricultural Studies*, and *Medical and Health Sciences* can be removed from the classification system, leaving the *Natural Sciences* and *Engineering and Technology*. This produces Figure 13.

Analysis of Figure 13 and the filtered dataset indicates there are 2,183 unique ontologies and 4,097 category classifications, an average of 1.9 categories per ontology which evidences that GPT-4o was following the instructed action of assigning more than one RA to each ontology where necessary, but also that there could be significant overlap between the research areas.

The Bio-associated OLSs such as BioPortal (orange) and BioRegistry (green) make up the majority of all classifications for each RA, with significant coverage of the filtered physical sciences EuroSciVoc NT1 categories. Furthermore, the domains of biology and chemistry are shown to have the greatest abundance of ontologies available to them, whereas materials science, physics, and industrial engineering, fall behind significantly and ontological availability and abundance is poor.

7 Conclusions & Future Work

This project forms an initial exploration into the semantic landscape of the physical sciences, with a particular focus on ontological availability for different domains/research areas within the field. The project produced four considered ontologies key to foundational areas within the physical sciences for further exploration by PSDI, in particular the establishment of the EuroSciVoc ontology as a conclusive and reliable controlled vocabulary for defining the domains within the physical sciences. 11 online-accessible ontology repositories were analysed for the ontologies they contain via a web-scraping tool, followed by the utilisation of the GPT-4o LLM to categorise the ontologies based on a subset of the EuroSciVoc Research Areas. Graphical analysis of the output data indicated regions of ontological sparsity, in particular the domains of materials science, and physics. Conversely, it also highlighted regions of ontological abundance such as in the biological sciences, and chemical sciences.

The study would benefit from the employment of a further two LLMs (GEMINI and Copilot) to follow the same categorisation process as established with GPT-4o. This was initially planned within the methodology but time constraints prevented this from happening; performing this would provide more certainty and credibility to the classifications applied, increasing the validity of the conclusions drawn from the data analysis.

In addition to this, a continuation to the project would be to expand the metadata analysis of each of the ontologies through increasing the number of datapoints collected for each ontology during the web-scraping process. Examples including the update frequency, and number of projects on which the ontology is currently being used, could indicate the relative "usefulness" of the ontology. Moreover, further meta-analysis to the ontologies themselves has the potential to produce interesting results to the quality of the available ontologies; metrics such as number of classes, properties, and mappings, could infer how "complete" the ontology is and whether it covers the Research Area in-depth which would aid its implementation in research.

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9 Outputs, Data & Software Links

A .zip file containing the outputs of this project has been attached to the Zenodo Record for this report. The RDM structure for the project is approximately in chronological order, with `XX-[NAME]` being the top-level structure for each folder. No specialised software was used for this software aside from openly available Python libraries for use in Jupyter Notebooks.

- **00.Deliverables:** This folder contains the deliverables for the internship project, including a summary of the literature search exercise, a copy of the two presentations of work (interim, final) given during this internship, and a copy of the poster presented during the Undergraduate Poster Presentation Day. A copy of this report will also be within this folder.
- **01.OntologyScraping:** This folder contains the Jupyter Notebooks (`.ipynb`) for the ontology scraping scripts using the Selenium Webdriver utility. It also contains the raw output of each of the scrapers.
- **02.OntologyClassification:** This folder contains the classification methodology produced by GPT-4o in a `.txt` format, as well as the merged spreadsheet of ontologies submitted to the LLM for classification.
- **03.OntologyAnalysis:** This folder contains another Jupyter Notebook containing the data analysis code, producing graphic outputs using the `matplotlib` library.
- **04.EPSRC-to-EuroSciVoc-mapping:** This folder contains the mappings from the EPSRC research area categories to the EuroSciVoc NT1 categories.
- **05.misc:** This folder contains miscellaneous outputs from the project, including some unfinished research into the EuroVoc ontology (different to EuroSciVoc), a useful paper on HQDM, and a copy of the European Research Information Ontology.
- **OntologyList:** This spreadsheet is the collection of all of the useful data within the project merged into one. It is where the full list of analysed ontologies is, pre- and post-duplicate removal, and contains a copy of all of the raw ontology scraping outputs "hidden" for brevity but can be accessed by un-hiding the sheets.

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